

SoTL in Civil and Structural Engineering Systematic Review Search Strategy

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Experienced Researcher: Dr. Alejandro Jiménez Rios

Main Supervisor: Prof. Vagelis Plevris

Secondment Supervisor: Prof. Maria Nogal

Collaborator: Prof. Wilhelm Friedrich Admiraal

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1 Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review Literature Search (PRISMA-S)

1.1 Introduction

Systematic reviews quality heavily relies in the search strategy implemented for the information retrieval process. Nevertheless, search strategies are commonly not adequately reported. This document presents the search strategy adopted to perform the systematic review of the SoTL in Civil and Structural Engineering and it is based on the PRISMA-S [1] checklist.

1.2 Search strategy

The recommended items to address in a search strategy according to the PRISMA-S checklist are presented in Table 1, Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4. This search strategy has been developed and documented to ensure transparency of the systematic review and facilitate its reproducibility.

Table 1. Information sources and methods.

Database name:	The following electronic database was searched: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scopus. • Web of Science. • OsloMet Library. • Google Scholar.
Multi-database searching:	Not applicable.
Study registries:	The following electronic registry was searched: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OSF Registries.
Online resources and browsing:	No records from online browsing will be included due to the lack of rigor of the found results and the difficulty of reproducing search results.
Citation searching:	The search will focus on the main sources only as it is intended to present a review with the outmost state-of-the-art available knowledge.
Contacts:	No further details will be searched by directly contacting authors, experts, manufacturers, or others.
Other methods:	Relevant research part of the personal electronic libraries of the authors will also be considered on this systematic review.

Table 2. Search strategies.

Full search strategy:	Scopus search: Relevant initial keywords and similar terms of interest (namely: "scholarship of teaching and learning" and sotl, etc.) were used. The query was performed as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TITLE-ABS-KEY (("engineer*" OR "civil engineer*" OR "structural engineer*") AND ("scholarship of teaching and learning" OR sotl)). Web of Science search: ALL=(("engineer*" OR "civil engineer*" OR "structural engineer*") AND ("scholarship of teaching and learning" OR sotl)) OsloMet Library search: Any field: contains: "engineer*" OR "civil engineer*" OR "structural engineer*" AND Any field: contains: "scholarship of teaching and learning" OR sotl Google Scholar search: ("engineer*" OR "civil engineer*" OR "structural engineer*") AND ("scholarship of teaching and learning" OR sotl) OSF Registries search: The full title of the systematic review was searched: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scholarship of Teaching and Learning in Civil and Structural Engineering: A Systematic Review.
Limits and restrictions:	No limits nor restrictions were applied in the search.
Search filters:	The Scopus search was limited to the search fields of title, abstract and keywords.
Prior work:	The search strategy adopted has been created specifically for this systematic review. No search strategies from previous literature reviews have been adopted.
Updates:	No update method will be used as the final manuscript will be completed shortly after the search had been performed.

Dates of searchers:	The search was conducted on 01/09/2023.
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Table 3. Peer review.

Peer review:	The search strategy document will be made available online along with the systematic review protocol in the OSF website. Both documents are available to receive open peer reviews under the Resources tab of the project Registry website [2].
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Table 4. Managing records.

Total records:	A total of 34182 records were found (Scopus: 84, Web of Science: 43, OsloMet Library 55, Google Scholar:34000). The OSF Registries search returned 45 516 results.
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Deduplication:	Deduplication was performed with the automatic detection tool available while importing RIS files into EndNote (only Scopus, Web of Science, and OsloMet Library records were downloaded in RIS format and imported into EndNote). Further manual check was performed by sorting all records added by title. The first 50 pages of results (500 more relevant records) found in Google Scholar were manually inspected.
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References

1. Rethlefsen, M.L., et al., *PRISMA-S: an extension to the PRISMA Statement for Reporting Literature Searches in Systematic Reviews*. *Systematic Reviews*, 2021. **10**(1): p. 39 DOI: 10.1186/s13643-020-01542-z.
2. Jiménez Rios, A. *Scholarship of Teaching and Learning in Civil and Structural Engineering Registry*. 2023.DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/YZTD3>.

Annex A

Table 5. History of changes.

Version	Publication date	Change
1.0	12/10/2023	Initial version.

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